

Effects of agronomical selenium biofortification of Iberian pig diet on quality and antioxidant capacity of pork

F.I. Hernández-García, J. Matías, M. López-Parra, J. García-Gudiño, C. Barraso, N. Garrido, A.M. García-Calvo, M. Izquierdo

Center of Scientific & Technological Research of Extremadura (CICYTEX), Spain

Corresponding author: Francisco Ignacio Hernández-García (francisco.hernandez@juntaex.es)

ABSTRACT

Due to its valuable high intramuscular fat content and lipid composition, Iberian pork is very prone to rancidity. Selenium (Se) supplementation delays meat post-mortem oxidation, but organic Se reaches tissues more efficiently and durably than the inorganic forms, which may even be toxic at high concentrations. Agronomical Se biofortification (incorporating Se to crops) provides organic Se, is not expensive and is effective and safe for producing animal feed and human food. This study aimed to: 1) Determine the effectiveness of Se-biofortification in triticale crops. 2) Evaluate the use of Se-biofortified triticale grain in Iberian pigs during the pre-finishing vs the pre-finishing + finishing periods to determine the permanence of Se and the effects on pork antioxidant capacity. A 4-ha triticale plot was sprayed with sodium selenate (10 g Se/ha) and a similar, control plot was not sprayed. Treated plot grain had greater Se concentration ($430 \pm 22 \mu\text{g Se/kg}$) than that from the control one ($< 125 \mu\text{g}$). Starting at 7 months of age (**m**), castrated Iberian pigs were fed with standard concentrate, containing 45% of triticale, which was standard (Control; **Ctrl**, n=10), or the Se-biofortified one (Treated groups; **Trt**), which were fed until they were 12 m (**Se-1**; n=9) or until slaughter time (60 days later; **Se-2**; n=10). Blood samples were collected at the end of

the finishing period for Se content and metabolic parameters. Pre-slaughter loin and gluteal ultrasonography was performed. Carcass and prime cuts were weighed, and meat samples stored for Se content and meat quality analyses (before and after 7-day maturation; **d0** and **d7** respectively). Meat Se content was greater in Trt vs Ctrl, and greater in Se-2 vs Se-1. Treatment did not affect body weight nor blood Se content, but it increased ultrasonographic subcutaneous fat thickness in Se-1 and triglyceride blood levels in Se-2. In Se-1 and Se-2, loin pH on d0 was higher, and L* and b* color values at d7 were lower. In addition, cooking losses were lower for Se-1 on d0. Loin TBARS was greater (more oxidized pork) at d7 in Ctrl. Pork springiness and resilience were greater for Se-2 at 20% compression. These results suggest (for the first time, as far as we know) a great potential for this sustainable strategy to increase meat antioxidant capacity through agronomical selenium biofortification for animal feeding and for Iberian pigs in particular, even after a 2-month period of concentrate withdrawal, which is required for *montanera*-finished (free-ranging, acorn-fed) animals.

Keywords: heavy pigs; meat rancidity; organic selenium; extensive systems; sustainability; triticale.

Highlights:

- Agronomically selenium (Se)-biofortified triticale was used for pig diets.
- These Se-biofortified diets increased the antioxidant capacity of Iberian pork.
- These biofortified diets increased Se in meat but not in blood plasma.
- Main meat effects persisted for 2 months after biofortified diet withdrawal.
- This biofortification was inexpensive, safe and with long lasting effects.

1. Introduction

Selenium (Se), a trace element, is an essential dietary nutrient for humans and animals, because it participates in the regulation of various physiological functions as an integral part of selenoproteins (Zhang et al., 2010). Selenium deficiency in the population is a universal problem. Combs (2001), on the basis of the available worldwide data on selenium concentration in human blood, classified countries into three groups according to the percentage of their population with a deficient selenium level: low (<10%), moderate (10-50%) and high (>50%). According to this, Spain would be in the latter category.

There are several options studied to increase the daily intake of selenium. According to Lyons et al. (2005), these would be: 1) increased consumption of foods rich in selenium, 2) addition of selenium to drinking water; 3) individual intake of pharmacological preparations; 4) selenium fortification processes in food manufacturing; 5) biofortification. The latter would include the use of selenium as a fertilizer for crops (agronomic biofortification; see Figure 1) and the genetic improvement of certain crops to increase their efficiency in selenium absorption from the soil (genetic biofortification). The only method that has shown satisfactory results so far has been the agronomic biofortification (Garg et al., 2018).

Feeding strategies are widely used in animals to improve meat quality. Many of these interventions have focused on dietary supplementation with antioxidants such as Se and/or vitamin E. Dietary Se supplementation has been reported to have antioxidant activities and to be effective in delaying post-mortem oxidation reactions, especially in its organic form (Mahan et al., 2014). Selenium may be administered as an injection or in the feed with its mineral supplements, with Se provided as inorganic sodium selenite

or selenate. One limitation of supplementing with inorganic Se is the short duration of the storage of this element in the animal (Burk, 2007).

Natural Se sources in plants are organic forms, e.g., selenomethionine, selenocysteine, or Se-methylselenocysteine. When inorganic Se is fed to animals, selenocysteine is the main seleno-compound formed (Rayman et al., 2008). In contrast, when using organic Se it is possible to build Se reserves in the body, which are subsequently available during stress conditions when the Se requirement is increased but feed consumption is decreased (Burk, 2007). The potential for using Se-containing fertilizers to increase feed Se concentrations and, therefore, dietary Se intake has been demonstrated in Finland, New Zealand and Australia, where it has proven to be both effective and safe (reviewed by Broadley et al., 2006). The same has also been demonstrated in Mediterranean conditions with durum wheat (Poblaciones et al., 2014).

Cereals are the main components of pig concentrates. In several studies, the levels of Se in the cereal grain have been successfully increased by spraying small amounts of inorganic Se solution (Lyons et al., 2005). Poblaciones et al. (2014) obtained a strong linear relationship between the dose rates of Se application and the total Se and Se-Methionine content in grain, resulting in an increase of Se concentrations close to those recommended in foodstuffs when using a dose of 10 g Se/ha of sodium selenate applied as a foliar spray at the end of tillering (lateral shot emergence).

Selenium role in animal health is based on the functions of selenoproteins, many of which have antioxidant activities (Zhang et al., 2023 and 2010), and one of the most important is the glutathione reductase, an enzyme that protects the cell against oxidative stress. It has been observed that Se supplement in the diet has antioxidant activity and is effective in delaying postmortem oxidation reactions, especially the organic Se form,

because it reaches the tissues more efficiently (Jang et al., 2010; Mahan et al., 2014), thus resulting in a better water retention capacity and color in pork meat (Zhan et al., 2007). The quality of pork depends on attributes such as water retention capacity, color and oxidative stability, which are decisive in its processing and storage (Calvo et al., 2016).

The objectives of the present study were the following: 1) To determine the effectiveness of Se-biofortification in triticale crops. 2) To evaluate the use of Se-biofortified triticale grain in Iberian pigs, either during the pre-finishing period only or during the pre-finishing and finishing periods, to determine the permanence of the Se provided by this way and also the effects of this biofortification strategy on the antioxidant capacity of pork. The degree of this Se permanence will determine the possibility of using this sustainable procedure before the *montanera* (free-ranging acorn feeding finishing period) and still decreasing pork rancidity.

2. Materials and Methods

All experimental procedures were in compliance with the European Union regulations concerning the protection of animals used for experimental and other scientific purposes (Directive 2010/63/EU).

2.1. Agronomical biofortification of triticale

A field experiment was conducted during the triticale growing season (winter) at the experimental farm “Valdesequera” (39° 3' 13.2", -6° 50' 45.2"), belonging to CICYTEX, located in Southwestern Spain. Plants were grown in a typical *dehesa* soil. Soil was harrowed before sowing. Around 8 ha were sown with triticale (\times *Triticosecale*) in December at a dose rate of 180 kg/ha in rows of 18 cm. The variety was *Verato*,

which was obtained by CICYTEX. Regarding fertilization, 300 kg/ha of an NPK complex fertilizer (8-15-15) were incorporated before sowing, and 50 UN/ha of calcium ammonium nitrate (27% N) were applied as top dressing in February. To evaluate the influence of Se fertilization on the crop, the whole plot was randomly divided into two blocks of approximately 4 ha (Control: without Se fertilization; Treated: with Se fertilization). The Se biofortification was carried out via foliar application at the end of the tillering stage (Zadoks' growth stage 30-39; beginning of stem elongation), using a Se fertilizer (sodium selenate from *Acros Organics* with 98 % purity) at a dose rate of 25g/ha of Se fertilizer (10.2 g/ha of Se), following the results reported by Poblaciones et al. (2014). In July, the harvest was mechanically conducted, and each treatment block was collected separately. From the harvested grain of each block, 12 samples of approximately 100 g each were randomly taken. Samples were stored at room temperature and dry conditions for further analyses.

2.2. *Animals, management, experimental design and zootechnical data collection*

A total of 30 castrate pure Iberian pigs (63.5 ± 1.1 kg body weight, **BW**; mean \pm SE; 8.1 months (**m**) old, 7.7 - 8.4 range; born from December-26 to January-15) were used in semiextensive conditions in this study. As depicted in Figure 2, the experiment was conducted during the prefinishing and finishing periods, from 7 to 14 months of age, with the animals divided in 3 treatment groups (according to diet as explained thereafter) and housed in 3 large outdoor corrals (99 x 21 m each; 10 animals/corral; 1 corral/treatment) provided with shadowed areas. At 7 months of age, animals were randomly assigned to treatment (in a stratified manner according to BW) to one of 3 treatment groups according to the diets that started at that age: 1) *Control* (**Ctrl**; n = 10), fed with a standard concentrate (containing 45% of regular triticale; Table 1) until the end of the finishing period. 2) *Selenium-1* (**Se-1**; n = 10), fed with the same type of

concentrate (but containing 45% of agronomically-biofortified triticale) up to 12 months of age and then fed the standard concentrate until the end of the finishing period. 3) *Selenium-2 (Se-2; n = 10)*, fed with the selenium-biofortified concentrate for 2 more months (60 days) until the end of the finishing period. Pigs were slaughtered with an age of 13.7 months (13.3-14.0 range) and a BW of 152.0 ± 2.2 kg.

Body weight was collected at the start of the experiment (~8 months of age) and monthly thereafter. Pre-slaughter inter-scapular and loin ultrasonography were performed with an ultrasound scanner (ALOKA-500SSD, ALOKA Inc., Tokyo, Japan) and a 12-cm, 3.5 MHz probe. Interscapular subcutaneous fat was measured over the middle of the interscapular space, from the top of the 2nd thoracic spinous apophysis to the skin. The transversal area of the *Longissimus dorsi (LD)* muscle (*L. thoracis*, more specifically) was measured at the 10th rib level (intercostal space between the 10th and 11th ribs), and the subcutaneous fat thickness (backfat) over this muscle was measured over the middle of this transversal section at this rib level (Ayuso et al., 2013). Blood plasma samples were collected after finishing (at ~14 months of age) for Se content and metabolic parameters.

After slaughter, weight of carcass and prime cuts (ham, foreleg and loin) were recorded. The yields (with respect to BW) of carcass, hams, forelegs, loins and total prime cuts were calculated. A portion of the left loin and its subcutaneous fat cover, with its adjacent skin, was extracted by cutting the carcass between the 10th and 14th ribs. This segment was used to measure the backfat thickness and the loin area at the 10th rib level. Intramuscular fat percentage (**IMF**) and meat texture parameters were assessed in loin samples at this rib level.

2.3. Meat quality analyses

After slaughter, *Longissimus dorsi* samples were taken and immediately frozen. Different meat quality parameters were analyzed, both on day 0 (just after thawing), and after 7 days (post-thawing) of maturation. This maturation was carried out in refrigeration at 4°C in plastic trays covered with transparent film. These procedures were carried out to determine the effect of treatment on the quality parameters analyzed and its persistence after maturation. The parameters analyzed were the following:

a) *Measurement of pH and instrumental color*: The pH was determined with a handheld, puncture pH-meter (Crison pH-meter model Micro pH 2001). The Minolta CR300 colorimeter was used to determine the color parameters lightness (L*), redness (a*) and yellowness (b*) in the CIE Lab color space coordinates, according to the methodology described by Cassens et al. (1995).

b) *Intramuscular fat (IMF)*: This end point was determined by the procedure of Folch et al. (1957), based on successive washings of meat samples with a mixture of chloroform and methanol (2:1), and final evaporation of the solvent for quantification by weighing the extracted fat. The fatty acid profile was determined by gas chromatography and a flame ionization detector (CG-FID) applied to the fatty acid methyl esters obtained by methylation in acidic medium (Cava et al., 1997).

c) *Lipid oxidation*: This parameter was determined by the **TBARS** (Thiobarbituric Acid Reactive Substance) assay, being spectrophotometrically analyzed by determining the substances reactive to thiobarbituric acid (**TBA**), according to Salih et al. (1987). Tetraethoxypropane (TEP) was used as the reference standard.

d) *Instrumental texture analysis*: Samples were previously vacuum-packed in bags (O_2 permeability of $9.3 \text{ ml } O_2 / \text{m}^2 / 24 \text{ h at } 0^\circ\text{C}$) and cooked by immersion in a water bath for 45 minutes at 75°C . Water cooking losses were calculated afterwards. In the

cooked samples, two types of measurements were made using a TA-XT2I Texture Analyzer (Stable Micro Systems Ltd., Surrey, UK): a) Warner-Bratzler shear force (WBSF) assessment for meat tenderness and texture profile analysis (TPA), using the method described by Bourne (1978) to quantify various physical properties such as hardness, adhesiveness, fracturability, cohesiveness, springiness, gumminess, chewiness and resilience, with a compression ratio of 20%, to determine the behavior of the myofibrillar structure; and b) TPA at 80% compression ratio to determine the behavior of the connective tissue.

2.4. Agronomical, metabolic and selenium content analyses

Concentrations of total Se in triticale grain and in pork were determined by using an inductively coupled plasma mass spectrometer (ICP-MS; Agilent 7500ce, Agilent Technologies, Palo Alto, CA, USA) operating in the Helium gas mode. This analytical method was performed at the Elemental and Molecular Analysis Service of the University of Extremadura (Spain).

To assess protein content of triticale grain, an elemental analyzer (Leco) was used to determine the content of N following the Dumas method, in which protein percentage was determined by multiplying the total N by 5.83 as a conversion factor.

Metabolic analyses in blood plasma samples were performed at the Laboratory of the University on León, Spain (*Laboratorio de Técnicas Instrumentales*, LTI, homologated following the ISO 9001:2015 requirements) using an automatic analyzer (Biosystems BA400) for chemical and biochemical parameters

2.5. Statistical analyses

A *Student t*-test was conducted to assess the influence of the fertilization with Se, comparing the Se content of samples of Control and Treated land plots. To assess treatment effects on the animals, data on pig growth and meat quality were subjected to one-way analysis of variance using the General Linear Models (GLM) procedure. The software used was SAS 9.3 and significance level was set at $P < 0.05$.

3. Results

3.1. Agronomical biofortification

The average grain yield was 1.3 t /ha. The average humidity content was 8%. The average crude protein was 11.6 %. The average Se content in the grain from the Treated plot ($429.5 \pm 6.33 \mu\text{g}/\text{kg}$) was significantly greater ($p = 0.025$) than that of the grain from the Control plot ($< 25.0 \mu\text{g}/\text{kg}$, below the detection limit). Grain yield and protein content were similar in Treated and Control plots.

3.2. Growth, carcass traits and selenium accumulation

As depicted in Table 2, BW and average daily gain (**ADG**) were not affected by treatment. However, there were some differences in ultrasound measurements for body composition, with the Se-1 group having thicker subcutaneous fat at the inter-scapular and loin levels. Loin area was not different among treatment groups.

Table 3 shows the *post-mortem* carcass traits: Carcass weight, length and yield showed no treatment differences, and neither did the prime cut yield nor the foreleg, ham and loin yields. Loin weight, loin area and loin backfat cover were not different among treatments. Similarly, no treatment differences were found for ham and foreleg weights.

Table 4 depicts blood plasma metabolic parameters: Glucose, cholesterol and LDL levels were not different among treatment groups. However, triglyceride levels were greatest for the Se-2 group.

Figure 3 depicts the blood Se levels, which were similar after finishing for the 3 treatment groups. Figure 4 shows the total content of Se in meat, with a greater concentration in the treated Se-2 group, a lower concentration in the Se-1 treated animals, and a much lower content in the Control group.

3.3. Meat quality

a) *Color, pH and cooking losses*: The treatments did not result in significant differences (Table 5) for the color parameters measured before maturation (on day 0 post-thawing), but after 7 days of maturation in refrigeration, the Treated groups had smaller lightness (L*) and yellowness (b*). Table 5 also shows the treatment effect on the pH measured in the *Longissimus dorsi* muscle, which was higher on day 0 and 7 post-maturation in the samples of pigs fed with the biofortified diet, with the only exception that the Se-1 group had intermediate values between Ctrl and Se-2. Water cooking losses (Table 6) were smaller for the Se-1 group than for the Controls, being intermediate for Se-2.

b) *Texture and intramuscular fat*: The values of instrumental shear force (Fmax) determined by the Warner-Bratzler device did not indicate treatment differences (data not shown). Table 6 shows that springiness at 20% compression rate determined by TPA reached significant differences among groups, with greater values in Se-2 vs Se-1 and Ctrl. Resilience at 20% compression rate was also greater for Se-2 vs Se-1, with Ctrl having intermediate values. Harness (at 20% and 80% compression rate), and springiness and resilience at 80% compression rate were not different among treatment

groups. The intramuscular fat content was not modified by the inclusion of Se in the diet.

c) Oxidation index: As can be seen in Figure 5, the oxidative stability, expressed as the production of substances reacting to thiobarbituric acid (TBARs), shows that the **MDA** (malondialdehyde) content with which it started on day 0 was close between groups but highly different statistically, with the Se-1 group having the lowest value compared with the other two groups. However, after a maturation period of 7 days, both groups supplemented with selenium exhibited values well below those of the Control group.

d) Fatty acids: Table 7 indicates the percentages of fatty acids (**FA**) grouped as saturated (**SFA**), monounsaturated (**MUFA**) and polyunsaturated (**PUFA**). There was no treatment effect on these FA profiles, neither on day 0 nor after 7 days of maturation.

4. Discussion

3.1. Agronomical biofortification

The crop results obtained indicate that biofortification of triticale with Se is feasible by spraying small amounts of mineral (inorganic) Se to the crop, as it was demonstrated in other winter cereals (Poblaciones et al., 2014). It should be noted that the Se content in grain reached 429.5 µg/kg, which is in line with that reported by Poblaciones et al. (2014) for durum wheat in a similar environment.

3.2. Growth, carcass traits and selenium accumulation

An effect of Se supplementation on ADG was not found in the present study. A somehow similar situation was reported by Speight et al. (2012), in whose study the dietary supplementation of boars with organic Se failed to alter ADG or ADFI (average

daily feed intake) but enhanced the gain:feed ratio during the growing and finishing phases. In relation to this, selenomethionine-supplemented diets resulted in higher feed intake (Falk et al., 2019). Although *postmortem*-measured backfat thickness was not affected in the present study, *in vivo* ultrasound subcutaneous thickness was greatest in two locations for the Se-1 group (after 2 months of organic Se supplementation withdrawal). In another study, in relation to this, dorsal fat was thinner in pigs supplemented with organic Se at high doses (0.4 mg/kg Se-enriched yeast; Calvo et al., 2016).

As for the blood metabolic parameters, triglyceride levels were greater for Se-2 animals. However, this parameter was within the physiological range (Bressan et al., 2022). The greater triglyceridemia in the Se-2 vs the Se-1 group may be due to the constant organic Se intake in the former. In relation to this, it has been shown that increased Se increases insulin production and release, thus decreasing glycemia and increasing triglyceridemia in pigs (Zhao et al., 2016) and decreasing glycemia in other species (Zhou et al., 2013). The fact that the loin subcutaneous fat and (more markedly) the inter-scapular subcutaneous fat, both measured by ultrasonography, were thicker in the Se-1 vs Se-2 groups seems consistent with a plausibly lower insulin level after 2 months of organic Se withdrawal in Se-1. Nevertheless, comparisons of Se supplementation effects among studies are often conflicting because of the type (organic or inorganic) and level of supplementation, because, for example, the metabolic effects of Se may be opposite depending on the intake level (Zhou et al., 2013).

In the present study, the base diet formulation (to which biofortified triticale substituted the standard triticale in the Treated concentrate) was relatively high in added Se (0.3 ppm; Table 1) and Vitamin E (as usual, e.g., Jlali et al., 2014). Therefore, this inorganic Se additive may have masked the effects of the organic Se contributed by the

biofortified triticale on growth performance or other parameters, but we decided to keep the usual inorganic Se additive because we wanted to test the agronomical biofortification strategy vs the usual, commercial concentrates, which practically always contain a vitamin and mineral premix.

Maximum level of Se (inorganic from sodium selenite, or organic as Se-enriched yeast) in complete feeds has been set at 0.5 mg/kg (or ppm) in the European Union to ensure feed safety (as reviewed by Cao et al., 2014). Of all elements, selenium has one of the narrowest ranges between dietary deficiency (<40 µg/day) and toxic levels (>400 µg (0.4 mg) per day), which makes it necessary to carefully control intakes in both humans and animals (WHO, 1963). In the present study, the Se content in the biofortified triticale grain (0.4 ppm), biofortified concentrate (0.5 ppm), pork (0.18 ppm) and blood (0.29 ppm) fell between these EU and WHO approved ranges for inorganic Se. Moreover, since organic Se is more effective but safer, the limits might be not so critical. In addition, if the inorganic Se additive (0.3 ppm) was not used, the final Se content in the concentrate would have been lower.

In the present study, the positive effect of treatment in improving oxidation index (as discussed below in more detail) is further supported by the results found in the quantification of selenium in the muscles, since they reveal a higher concentration of said trace element in animals supplemented with selenium up to the slaughter phase (Se2), with a lower concentration of selenium in muscle in animals supplemented only during the pre-finishing phase (Se1) and much lower in the Control group. Furthermore, these results indicate that the antioxidant power of selenium is maintained over time, since the Se-1 group still presented a Se concentration in muscle higher than the Control group and an oxidation level similar to the Se-2 group, being this parameter greatest for the Control group. This may imply a great advantage for the production of Iberian pigs

under the "acorn-fed" (*montanera*) denomination, because, as indicated in the Iberian quality standard (RD 4/2014), the animals should be slaughtered after the exclusive use of natural resources provided by pasture and acorns, with a minimum duration of 60 days without any other supply of feed. Therefore, it would only be necessary to administer this type of agronomically biofortified feedstuff during the pre-finishing phase, before the free-range *montanera* finishing period, to favor the obtainment of high-quality meat with longer shelf-life.

On the other hand, taking into account that Control and Treated concentrates had the same mineral additives in their formulation (including inorganic Se), the absence of an effect of agronomical Se biofortification in the present study on Se blood plasma levels at the end of finishing suggests that this biofortification strategy poses no risk of toxicity for the animals.

3.3. Meat quality

a) Color: The absence of treatment effect on pork color on day 0 was similar to what happened in the study from Calvo et al. (2017). In the present study, the values found were much lower than those reported by Zhang et al. (2020) for pork after supplementation with 0.3mg/kg of organic and inorganic selenium, and also lower than those described by Calvo et al. (2017) for pigs supplemented with 0.4 mg/kg in the form of selenite sodium or selenomethionine for the L* and b* indices. However, the value of the a* index in this latter study was lower than in the present one and lower than those found by Añazco (2015), who also found no effect on the a* value for pork from animals supplemented with organic selenium and stored frozen for 4 months. Similarly, Skřivanová et al. (2007) did not find significant treatment effects on color parameters in calves that received different diets (control vs selenium-yeast supplementation at 0.5 ppm).

However, the measurements done after 7 days of maturation in the present study did find differences between treatment groups. The highest L* color values (paler meat) corresponded to the animals of the Control group. On the contrary, with other breeds of pigs, Bobček et al. (2004) found that meat from the animals fed with organic selenium (0.3 ppm) had greater lightness compared to those that did not receive selenium. In contrast, and similarly to the present study, Añazco (2015) found that pork of animals supplemented with organic selenium was darker and less pale. On the other hand, Vignola et al. (2009) found no effect on muscle lightness after supplementation of lambs with different sources of selenium.

In our study, no treatment differences were observed in terms of the a* index (redness) before or after maturation. In contrast, in relation to the b* index post-maturation, both groups of animals supplemented with selenium showed lower values (less yellowness) than those of the Control group. This may be due to a higher oxidation index in the Control group, since there is a close relationship between the levels of lipid oxidation and the oxidation of meat pigments, because the free radicals formed in the process of lipid oxidation act as promoters of the heme pigment oxidation, contributing to the conversion of oxymyoglobin to metamyoglobin (Gatellier et al., 1995). The chemical state of myoglobin has been related to the parameter b* in lean meats (Pérez-Álvarez et al., 1998).

b) pH: This parameter is related to color, water retention capacity and texture. Zhang et al. (2020) found a positive correlation of pH with water retention capacity, redness and tenderness, while it was negatively correlated with lightness and drip losses. The ideal pH of pork is between 5.8 and 6.3. Within these values, meat with a higher pH has better water retention properties (Algarrañaz & Luis, 2007). In the present study, Se supplementation resulted in higher pH values in LD muscle of Se-1 and Se-2

groups, coinciding with Añazco (2015), who observed that, after 4 months of freezing, the pH values of loins from pigs fed with a diet containing organic selenium were higher than in those fed without it. Zhan et al (2007) pointed out a slight trend for an increase in the pH values in pigs supplemented with sodium selenite and selenomethionine. However, Calvo et al. (2016), working also with a conventional pig genotype, found no differences in pork pH between groups fed with different sources of selenium (organic and inorganic), also obtaining pH values lower than those of the present study.

c) Cooking losses: Water is lost in meat as a result of cell membrane rupture with oxidation and over time. The loss of water has a detrimental effect on the visual and organoleptic properties of meat (Añazco, 2015). Organic Se has been reported to increase water retention capacity (Lisiak et al., 2014), although other authors did not find an effect in pork. For example, Calvo et al (2016) did not observe differences in estimated drip water losses in frozen-thawed muscle of pigs fed with diets supplemented with organic or inorganic Se. The decrease in water losses could be due to the antioxidant effect of Se that protects membrane integrity, since this element is essential for the antioxidant enzyme system, also interacting with vitamin E in cell membranes and consequently reducing water losses. In this regard, Mahan et al. (1999) suggested that excessive cell damage resulting from oxidation may be the cause of drip losses.

In the present study, the lower water loss after cooking in the Treated groups may be related to the pH of the meat, since water, being a polar molecule, is attracted to charged molecules such as proteins. When meat pH approaches the isoelectric point of proteins (5.4 for myosin), the charges become neutralized and therefore the water retention power decreases and losses increase (Huff-Lonergan & Lonergan, 2005). In

our study, the Control group had a pH close (<6) to the isoelectric point of myosin and also had the greatest losses after cooking, while the other two groups (Se-1 and Se-2) had higher values (>6) and, plausibly because of this, the losses after cooking were lower.

d) Meat texture and intramuscular fat: The lack of a treatment effect on hardness in the present study is contrasting with the results reported by Añazco (2015), who observed lower values of meat hardness in pigs that were supplemented with organic selenium. The same effect was observed by Rossi et al. (2013) when supplementing pig diets with antioxidant plant extracts. In contrast, Alberti et al. (2005) found no effect of antioxidant supplementation (plant extracts or vitamin E) on meat hardness in calves. The treatment effects on springiness and resilience at 20% but not at 80% compression rates may suggest that organic Se in muscle is mainly stored in muscular fibers and the amount possibly stored in the connective tissue does not affect its tensile properties.

Intramuscular fat in pork is highly accepted by the consumer, since it has a beneficial effect on the quality and sensory properties of the meat, thus improving tenderness, aroma and juiciness (Muriel et al., 2004). In the present study, the IMF content was not affected by treatment, and its values were above those found by Muriel et al. (2004) in Iberian pigs.

e) Oxidation index: Lipid oxidation and physicochemical changes are the main causes of meat deterioration, determining changes in flavor, texture, color and nutritional value, as well as the formation of potentially toxic compounds (Rossi et al., 2013). The evolution of the TBARS index in pork is highly variable. Nevertheless, there is abundant information showing that the susceptibility of tissues to undergo oxidation processes depends on the diet. According to Warriss (2003), who determined optimal

TBA levels for meats below 0.5, our values would correspond to optimal quality meats. Moreover, in the present study, the positive treatment effect on oxidative stability expressed by the TBARS index (decreased MDA) after maturation was in agreement with the study from Añazco (2015), who tested organic selenium supplementation, also coinciding with reports on lambs by Vignola et al. (2009). These results highlight the role played by selenium against lipid oxidation mechanisms, since this trace element is an integral part of the enzyme glutathione peroxidase, which has a protective effect against oxidative damage (Li et al., 2011). Zhan et al. (2007) also reported that the loin of pigs that received selenium, regardless of the source (organic or not), had an increased glutathione transferase (**GSH-Px**) activity and decreased MDA content in the TBARS assay. However, some authors, such as Juniper et al. (2009), determined that GSH-Px has little or no potential to improve the oxidative stability of meat derived from beef or lamb, respectively. Therefore, the antioxidant effect of Se in meat may arise mainly from Se storage in structural muscle proteins within selenized aminoacids like selenomethionine (see Figure 1 diagram).

f) Fatty acids: In the present study, the lack of effect of Se supplementation on fatty acid profiles is in agreement with the study from Skřivanová et al. (2007), who found no effect of a diet with organic selenium (0.5 ppm) on the fatty acid profile of the *Longissimus thoracis et lumborum* muscle in calves. Similarly, Zao et al. (2016) found no effect of Se supplementation on intramuscular lipid profiles in pigs. In contrast, Añazco (2015) found (also in a conventional pig breed) that a diet supplemented with organic selenium led to a 6.25% increase in PUFA in pork, as well as a higher content of SFA and lower percentage of MUFA.

5. Conclusions

The use of concentrate feedstuff agronomically biofortified with selenium resulted in some changes in meat quality parameters, like some meat color values after 7 days of maturation, a reduced cooking water loss, and an increased pH. Also, Se supplementation increased the ultrasound-measured subcutaneous fat thickness at two anatomical locations in the Se-1 group (only supplemented during pre-finishing) and increased the post-finishing triglyceride blood levels in Se-2 group (supplemented during pre-finishing and finishing). Finally, and most importantly, this agronomical biofortification increased Se content in pork, even after 60 days of supplementation withdrawal, thus decreasing the predisposition to oxidation of pork, as evidenced by a lower degree of lipid oxidation in comparison with the Control group. This organic Se supplementation was inexpensive, safe and with long-lasting effects. Therefore, these results suggest (for the first time, as far as we know) a great potential for this sustainable strategy for increasing meat antioxidant capacity through agronomical selenium biofortification for animal feeding and for Iberian pigs in particular. Moreover, this have important implications for Iberian pig management in *montanera* (free-ranging acorn feeding) extensive finishing conditions, since concentrate feeding is not allowed during this period (lasting for at least 60 days) under the Spanish regulations for the highest product quality level. This high quality and the extensive rearing contribute to preservation of the *dehesa* natural ecosystem, to avoid depopulation of rural areas and to increase environmental sustainability.

Conflicts of interests

None.

Acknowledgements

This research was funded by FEDER funds and *Junta de Extremadura* (Spain). We thank M. A. Pérez, V. Cruz, S. Pardo, the laboratory personnel and the *Valdesequera* research farm staff for their technical assistance.

Author ORCIDs

F. I. Hernández-García: <https://orcid.org/0000-0003-2313-2762>

J. Matías: <https://orcid.org/0000-0001-5383-9035>

M. López-Parra: <https://orcid.org/0000-0002-1934-2858>

J. García-Gudiño: <https://orcid.org/0000-0002-2457-854X>

C. Barraso: <https://orcid.org/0000-0001-8148-9204>

N. Garrido: <https://orcid.org/0000-0002-0401-478X>

M. Izquierdo: <https://orcid.org/0000-0003-4307-880>

Author contributions

F.I. Hernández-García: Conceptualization, Data curation, Formal analysis, Funding acquisition, Investigation, Methodology, Project administration, Supervision, Visualization, Writing – original draft, Writing - review & editing. **J. Matías:** Conceptualization, Formal analysis, Investigation, Methodology, Project administration, Writing – original draft, Writing - review & editing. **M. López-Parra:** Data curation, Formal analysis, Investigation, Methodology, Writing – original draft, Writing - review & editing. **J. García-Gudiño:** Data curation, Investigation, Methodology, Writing - review & editing. **C. Barraso:** Data curation, Formal analysis, Investigation, Methodology, Writing – original draft, Writing - review & editing. **N. Garrido:** Formal analysis, Investigation, Methodology, Writing - review & editing.

A.M. García-Calvo: Conceptualization, Investigation, Methodology. **M. Izquierdo:** Formal analysis, Investigation, Methodology, Project administration, Writing - review & editing.

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Table 1. Nutritional composition and ingredients of the Control and Treated (agronomically biofortified with selenium) concentrate feedstuffs.

A) Nutritional composition:	Control	Biofortified
Dry matter	12.116 %	idem
Ash	5.046 %	idem
Crude protein	15.734 %	idem
Crude fat	2.628 %	idem
Crude fibre	4.920 %	idem
Neutral detergent fibre	14.680 %	idem
Metabolizable energy (swine)	3 053,321 kcal/kg	idem
Net energy (swine)	2 246,490 kcal/kg	idem
Total selenium (E8 additive + plant-based)	0.32 ppm	0.54 ppm
B) Ingredients. 1) General List:	Control	Biofortified
Triticale	45%, standard	Idem, biofortified
Corn	29.65%	idem
Sunflower flour	11%	idem
Soybean flour	9%	idem
Wheat bran	2.50%	idem
Calcium carbonate	0,70%	idem
Lard	0.60%	idem
Bicalcium phosphate, dehydrated	0.50%	idem
Mineral salt	0.50%	idem
NE-10F nucleus ("cerdos únicos" brand)	0.30%	idem
L-Lysine HCL	0.20%	idem
Enzymecomplex	0.05%	idem
B) Ingredients. 2) Additives:	Control	Biofortified
Lysine	0.868 %	idem
Methionine	0.260 %	idem
Calcium	0.868 %	idem
Phosphorus	0.571 %	idem
Sodium	0.185 %	idem
E4 (copper)	24.840 mg/kg	idem
E1 (iron)	156.833 mg/kg	idem
E5 (manganese)	68.324 mg/kg	idem
E6 (zinc)	154.520mg/kg	idem
E2 (potassium iodide)	0.402 mg/kg	idem
E8 (selenium)	0.308 mg/kg	idem
Vitamin A	5 000.000 UI/kg	idem
VitalminD3	1 000.000 UI/kg	idem
Vitamin E	31.946 mg/kg	idem
Beta-glucanase	250.000 Gluc/kg	idem
Beta-xylanase	560.000 Xyl/kg	idem
E321. Butylated hydroxytoluene (BHT)	0.144 mg/kg	idem
E320. Butylated hydroxyanisole (BHA)	0.024 mg/kg	idem
E324. ethoxyquin	0.053 mg/kg	idem
E562. sepiolite	0.123 %	idem

Table2. Effect of selenium (Se) supplementation (through agronomical biofortification) on growth and on pre-slaughter carcass traits predicted *in vivo* by ultrasound scanning.

Variable	Control	Se-1	Se-2	RMSE	P Value
Pre-slaughter BW	151.30	152.70	151.90	12.33	0.97
ADG, prefinishing	0.413	0.410	0.412	0.05	0.99
ADG, finishing	0.764	0.845	0.191	0.27	0.51
¹ Loin area	24.19	21.51	23.27	2.74	0.12
² Inter-scapular fat	7.11 ^b	8.92 ^a	7.76 ^b	1.18	0.01
² Loin back fat	7.04 ^b	8.02 ^a	6.54 ^b	1.01	0.01

Se-1 group: Se-supplemented during pre-finishing only. Se-2 group: Se-supplemented during pre-finishing and finishing. BW: body weight. ADG: average daily gain (during 2 periods).¹Loin at the 10th rib level. ²Subcutaneous fat thickness measured at the inter-scapular zone and the 10th rib level, respectively.

Table 3. Effect of selenium (Se) supplementation (through agronomical biofortification) on carcass traits.

Variable	Control	Se-1	Se-2	RMSE	P Value
Carcass weight	123.15	127,81	124.77	10.46	0.62
Carcass length	79.70	80.60	79.80	3.39	0.82
Carcass yield	81.40	83.66	82.23	3.25	0.33
Prime cuts' yield	20.48	19.90	20.18	0.66	0.18
Ham yield	11.56	10.98	11.22	0.51	0.06
Foreleg yield	4.66	7.57	7.55	0.30	0.71
Loin yield	1.26	1.35	1.42	0.16	0.11
Ham weight	14.24	14.05	13.98	1.42	0.92
Foreleg weight	9.43	9.66	9.41	0.83	0.78
Loin weight	1.55	1.72	1.77	0.26	0.17
¹ Loin area	21.57	21.73	24.59	4.50	0.26
¹ Loin back fat	6.74	7.60	6.90	1.08	0.21

Se-1 group: Se-supplemented during pre-finishing only. Se-2 group: Se-supplemented during pre-finishing and finishing. ¹Loin at the 10th rib level.

Table 4. Effect of selenium (Se) supplementation (through agronomical biofortification) on blood plasma metabolic parameters.

Variable	Control	Se-1	Se-2	RMSE	P Value
Glucose	84.36	85.83	88.85	8.40	0.49
Triglycerides	65.06 ^b	61.66 ^b	94.96 ^a	25.24	0.01
Cholesterol	162.37	154.11	161.0	35.91	0.87
HDL	87.50	78.05	72.01	16.19	0.12
LDL	63.20	65.65	69.23	19.07	0.77

Se-1 group: Se-supplemented during pre-finishing only. Se-2 group: Se-supplemented during pre-finishing and finishing.

Table 5. Effect of selenium (Se) supplementation (through agronomical biofortification) on color parameters and pH of pork loin on day 0 and 7 after maturation.

Variable	Day	Control	Se-1	Se-2	RMSE	P Value
L*	0	40.57	39.88	41.17	2.60	0.57
	7	40.67 ^a	36.66 ^b	37.66 ^b	3.24	0.03
a*	0	8.81	9.18	9.68	0.90	0.12
	7	7.84	7.16	7.03	1.49	0.44
b*	0	4.28	4.33	4.88	0.58	0.06
	7	4.97 ^a	3.61 ^b	3.59 ^b	1.18	0.02
pH	0	5.63 ^a	6.02 ^b	6.05 ^b	0.12	0.0001
	7	5.96 ^a	6.12 ^{ab}	6.37 ^b	0.32	0.03

Color: L* (lightness); a* (redness); b* (yellowness). Se-1 group: Se-supplemented during pre-finishing only. Se-2 group: Se-supplemented during pre-finishing and finishing.

Table 6. Effect of selenium (Se) supplementation (through agronomical biofortification) on meat quality of pork loin on day 0 (pre-maturation): % intramuscular fat, % cooking losses and meat texture parameters.

Variable	Control	Se-1	Se-2	RMSE	P Value
¹ Intramuscular fat	5.95	5.20	4.85	1.98	0.46
Cooking losses	23.90 ^a	19.95 ^b	21.86 ^{ab}	2.41	0.01
² Hardness-20	2.95	2.83	2.74	0.85	0.85
² Hardness-80	108.70	94.80	99.04	13.83	0.10
² Springiness-20	0.97 ^b	0.97 ^b	1.17 ^a	0.16	0.01
² Springiness-80	0.56	0.56	0.59	0.04	0.18
² Resilience-20	0.51 ^{ab}	0.49 ^b	0.54 ^a	0.04	0.02
² Resilience-80	0.17	0.17	0.18	0.02	0.62

Se-1 group: Se-supplemented during pre-finishing only. Se-2 group: Se-supplemented during pre-finishing and finishing. ¹Loin at the 10th rib level. ²TPA parameters at 20% and 80% compression rates: hardness (N); springiness (distance ratio); resilience (force ratio).

Table 7. Effect of selenium (Se) supplementation (through agronomical biofortification) on fatty acid profile of pork loin on day 0 and 7 after maturation.

Variable	Control	Se-1	Se-2	RMSE	P Value
SFA-day 0	37.41	35.22	34.67	0.63	0.93
SFA-day 7	33.54	35.77	35.14	0.65	0.83
MUFA-day 0	59.89	58.96	59.31	0.56	0.82
MUFA-day 7	60.07	58.07	58.69	0.59	0.89
PUFA-day 0	5.40	5.82	6.02	0.16	0.31
PUFA-day 7	5.32	5.08	5.30	0.16	0.52

Se-1 group: Se-supplemented during pre-finishing only. Se-2 group: Se-supplemented during pre-finishing and finishing. SFA: saturated fatty acids. MUFA: monounsaturated fatty acids. PUFA: polyunsaturated fatty acids.

FIGURE CAPTIONS

Figure 1. Procedure and mechanism of agronomical biofortification with selenium, applied to triticale and the Iberian pig in the particular case of the present study. 1, 2: Pulverization with inorganic selenium (Se) just before stem elongation. 3: Organic Se spreads throughout the whole plant, including the grain. 4: In the plant, Se substitutes sulfur (S) in sulfur-containing aminoacids (e.g., methionine) resulting in organic Se storage. 5, 6: The organic Se appears in the grain and in the concentrate. 7, 8: Organic Se is stored in the animal and in the meat (in structural proteins and in selenoprotein antioxidant enzymes). *Illustrations from the authors (drawings: F.I.H.G.).*

Figure 2. Experimental design and chronogram of Control and Selenium (Se) -Treated Iberian pigs. Treated pigs were fed with concentrate containing triticale agronomically biofortified with Se (Treated concentrate) during pre-finishing only (Se-1 group) or during pre-finishing and finishing (Se-2 group). Control pigs and Se-1 group during finishing were fed with commercial Control concentrate containing regular triticale.

Figure 3. Agronomical biofortification of concentrate feedstuff with selenium (Se) in Iberian pigs: blood plasma Se content (means \pm SE) after the finishing phase. Ctrl: Control group. Se1: Treated group receiving Se supplementation only in 1 phase (pre-finishing). Se2: Treated group receiving Se supplementation in 2 phases (pre-finishing and finishing). No treatment differences were shown ($p=0.99$).

Figure 4. Agronomical biofortification of concentrate feedstuff with selenium (Se) in Iberian pigs: meat Se content (means \pm SE) after the finishing phase. Ctrl: Control group. Se1: Treated group receiving Se supplementation only in 1 phase (pre-finishing). Se2: Treated group receiving Se supplementation in 2 phases (pre-finishing and finishing). Treatment differences ($p=0.0001$) were shown among the 3 groups.

Figure 5. Agronomical biofortification of concentrate feedstuff with selenium (Se) in Iberian pigs: TBARs values in meat (means \pm SE) after the finishing phase on day 0 and 7 post-thawing (7 days of maturation). TBARs: oxidative stability expressed as the production of substances reactive with thiobarbituric acid (TBA). MDA: malondialdehyde. Ctrl: Control group. Se1: Treated group receiving Se supplementation only in 1 phase (pre-finishing). Se2: Treated group receiving Se supplementation in 2 phases (pre-finishing and finishing). Treatment differences were shown for Se1 vs Se2 and Ctrl on D0 ($p=0.0001$), and for Ctrl vs Se1 and Se2 on D7 ($p=0.0001$).